

THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL WAQF IN THE MODERN DEVELOPMENT OF LOCAL COMMUNITIES: THE ROLE AND EXPERIENCES OF THE WAQF DIRECTORATE OF THE ISLAMIC COMMUNITY IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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Abstract

The paper examines the historical and modern role of agricultural waqfs in Bosnia and Herzegovina, particularly through the efforts of the Waqf Directorate of the Islamic Community. Agricultural waqfs have the potential to drive socio-economic development by supporting local food production, providing employment, and fostering self-sustainable projects in rural and suburban communities. The document highlights successful initiatives like grain sowing, fruit planting, and greenhouse production as examples of waqfs fulfilling both economic and religious responsibilities. Despite these achievements, challenges such as land fragmentation, low profitability, and limited agricultural infrastructure hinder the full potential of waqfs. Addressing these issues through strategic planning and investment is necessary for future growth. Agricultural waqfs could play a crucial role in reducing rural depopulation, strengthening local economies, and contributing to social cohesion if supported by the Islamic Community and relevant authorities.

Keywords: Waqf, Waqf Directorate, Agriculture, Development

INTRODUCTION

Since the arrival of the Ottomans in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the *Waqf* (endowment) has played a significant role in driving economic and social development. With the formation of cities around *Waqfs* and the growing trust among the local population, the *Waqf* structure provided for all the population's needs (employment, religious needs, markets, social needs, etc.). With the departure of the Ottomans, there was a shift in the government's attitude toward *Waqfs*, leading to a neglectful approach and the widespread confiscation of *Waqfs* by the then-authorities, for whose restitution the Islamic Community in Bosnia and Herzegovina, as the legal custodian of *Waqfs*, is still waiting. The restoration of destroyed *Waqfs* and the establishment of new ones to meet the contemporary needs of Bosnia and Herzegovina's citizens have led *Waqfs* into a new era of prosperity.

The purpose of this paper is to present the experiences and role of the Waqf Directorate in revitalizing and advancing agricultural *Waqfs*, with a focus on the challenges it faces, and to consider the current and future role of this type of *Waqf* in the development of local communities in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

The paper outlines the structure and characteristics of *Waqf* land in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the foundations and opportunities for developing agricultural *Waqfs*, followed by the completed projects of the Waqf Directorate and local structures of the Islamic community (*Majlises*) aimed at strengthening the potential of agricultural *Waqfs*. The paper addresses the challenges of initiating and developing agriculture, considering the characteristics of *Waqfs*, the economic feasibility of investing in this type of *Waqf*, and the development prospects for the future. The results of relevant research are included and contextualized in the paper. The methods used in the paper are textual analysis, historical, and comparative methods.

AGRICULTURAL WAQF AND ISLAMIC VALUES

Until the Industrial Revolution, agriculture was the most important economic sector, driving and sustaining nations and civilizations. With the development of technology and the adoption of philosophies focused on maximizing profit, the economic aspect of agriculture became particularly emphasized, often being compared with the profitability of other sectors. Consequently, in countries with pronounced urbanization, agriculture took on a secondary significance, while industrial production and the use of various means for treating agricultural products raised questions about *halal*—the permissibility of consuming different types of food, the health aspects, and the price of organic food. Agricultural land fulfils Islamic values and the objectives of Sharia law in several ways:

1. Ensuring the economic and infrastructural development of the community at various levels, which is the primary goal of the *Waqf* as an institution. This can be seen in the Prophet's (PBUH) advice to Umar (RA) regarding the establishment of the first *Waqf*: "Make the property a *Waqf* that cannot be sold, gifted, or inherited, and its income should be used for the public good!" (Bukhari, 2772);
2. Providing healthy and *halal* food, which is a Quranic principle derived from the verse: "Eat of the good and lawful things that Allah has provided for you." (Qur'an, 16:114), a principle that has become particularly relevant with globalization and the existence of Muslims in societies unfamiliar with the principles of *halal* consumption;
3. Promoting solidarity, achieved by using resources like land and its revenues for the common good;
4. Using land as one of God's blessings for lawful purposes;
5. Cultivating and utilizing land (*imaret*) as one of the fundamental tasks of humankind in this world.

AGRICULTURAL WAQF AND THE LOCAL COMMUNITY

Agricultural *Waqfs* are directly linked to the development of rural and suburban areas. In the past, these *Waqfs* supported agricultural production in local communities, strengthening the community's microeconomy. The local population had access to *Waqf* land, contributing to their own livelihood, while the income from renting and selling produce was reinvested into the community and used for further development of the *Waqf*. This model provided an economic foundation for the community as well as its advancement. The potential of agricultural *Waqfs* in the development of rural and suburban areas remains significant even today: from an economic perspective, *Waqfs* offer opportunities for local self-employment on *Waqf* estates, increased local food production, and reduced dependency on imports, as well as the establishment of local producers' cooperatives. From a social perspective, *Waqfs* can provide food distribution and the opportunity to organize humanitarian projects, such as free meals for the poor. From a religious perspective, *Waqfs* enable the performing of various acts considered good deeds and promoting and upholding different Islamic values.

The Structure of Waqf Land in Bosnia and Herzegovina

Arable land is a valuable asset for its owners. Throughout history, various authorities have recognized this and unjustly seized vast *Waqf* properties. In the context of Bosnia and Herzegovina, a significant event was the Agrarian reform implemented by the Kingdom of SHS, which resulted in the confiscation of land equal to one-third of the total area of Bosnia and Herzegovina (all land that was not directly cultivated but rented was taken), as well as a set of laws from the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (SFRY), which confiscated real-estate (any real-estate that was not used for strictly religious purposes) that had not been previously seized, eventually leading to the dissolution of the Waqf Directorate.

It was only after the end of the aggression on Bosnia and Herzegovina in 1996 that the Waqf Directorate was re-established, taking over the responsibilities it had before being dissolved, protecting *Waqfs* from further seizure and decline, and restoring destroyed *Waqfs* while establishing new ones. In less than 30 years, the *Waqf* in Bosnia and Herzegovina has gained new momentum thanks to both domestic and foreign donors, as well as the dedicated individuals who have worked for the benefit of the *Waqf*.

Historians tell us that in the past, more than one-third of agricultural land, and sometimes even half of the buildings in major cities across the Islamic world (Egypt, Palestine, Syria, Turkiye), were *Waqf* properties. Today, *Waqf* revenues are often insufficient even to cover mosque maintenance, requiring state budget subsidies for ministries of *waqf* in most Muslim countries (Kahf, 2003). In Bosnia and Herzegovina, the *Waqf* was once a very powerful institution that spurred the development of local communities, transforming them from neighbourhoods into bazaars, towns, and even cities.

Today, *Waqfs* in Bosnia and Herzegovina mostly have enough resources for self-financing, but not for reconstruction and adaptation projects. They rely on new investments in *Waqf* assets through public calls for incentives from various levels of government, support from donors within Bosnia and Herzegovina, and support from donors and organizations abroad as well.

Agricultural *Waqf* land, thanks to new endowments after the war, now represents a significant potential for the development of local religious communities (*Jamaat*) and surrounding areas. In terms of the number of land plots, agricultural land makes up about 43% of the total number of *Waqfs* in Bosnia and Herzegovina, accounting for 83.76% of the total *Waqf* area in the country, covering over 35 million square meters. However, a large portion of this land does not generate income, with rental revenues from the land representing only 1.13% of total *Waqf* income in 2022 and 1.59% in 2023 (Strategy for development of Waqf and the Waqf Directorate of the IC in B&H 2025-2034, 2024).

The reasons for this low revenue share from agricultural *Waqfs* lie in the fact that agricultural land, as a primary sector of the economy, generates less income than properties used for rental purposes. Additionally, the land plots vary in quality and yield, as do the agricultural crops grown on them. Lastly, the distance from populated areas and roads, as well as the geographic location, affect the feasibility of leasing or cultivating the land, all of which result in significantly lower income and raise questions about the profitability of cultivating *Waqf* land and investing in it.

Graph 1

STRUCTURE OF WAQFS IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA: NUMBER OF LAND PLOTS BY CATEGORY

Summary overview of waqf property in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Data was taken from the Waqf Directorate database.

CULTIVATION PROJECTS

Projects of the Waqf Directorate

The Waqf Directorate is the institution that, according to the Constitution of the Islamic Community (IC), manages *Waqf* properties in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Although its primary focus is not agriculture, this aspect of its work is significant due to several reasons: the religious and constitutional obligation to maintain and develop *Waqfs*; the prominent role that *Waqf* has traditionally played in providing halal food; the current potential of this branch of the economy to benefit the *Waqf*; the crucial role of agriculture in the future to provide food for a growing global population; and the ongoing demand for healthy and halal food.

Due to the physical impossibility of directly managing all *Waqfs*, the Waqf Directorate manages them through local municipalities of the IC (*Majlises*), which find ways to utilize *Waqf* properties, while all legal and administrative matters such as establishing new endowments, rental agreements, etc., require the approval of the Waqf Directorate.

The Waqf Directorate, in cooperation with several *Majlises*, has so far implemented several projects for the cultivation of *Waqf* agricultural land. It is not possible to precisely estimate the long-term success of these projects, due to the lack of comprehensive data and measurable indicators of success across all the *Majlises* where these projects were implemented.

1. Spring Sowing Project

Since 2012, the Waqf Directorate, based on its planned activities and the large areas of unused *Waqf* land (primarily less promising plots), has initiated concrete activities in reviving *Waqfs*. In cooperation with several *Majlis* municipalities, it implemented a pilot project for cultivating scarce crops on *Waqf* land. Initially, non-grafted saplings were planted without irrigation systems, as funds were allocated only for the purchase of saplings. Several years after the planting, representatives of the Waqf Directorate visited some of the *Majlises* (Breza, Gračanica-Visoko, Goražde, Olovo, etc.) involved in the pilot project to assess the condition of the crops. Unfortunately, most of the crops did not succeed, primarily due to human factors, as the saplings were not properly or professionally maintained, and the lack of an irrigation system. After assessing the situation, the Waqf Directorate responded immediately. In the next phase of the project (2019), it insisted that *Majlis* partners ensure professional consultations and assign a person to continuously oversee the crops. Additionally, irrigation systems and other necessary supplies were provided, significantly improving the results of the plantings. Successful implementations of this project were carried out by *Majlises* municipalities in Fojnica, Bratunac, Vlasenica, Tešanj, Kakanj, Visoko, Bugojno, Bijeljina, Janja, and others. In 2019 alone, over 25 tons of

various fruits, vegetables, and grains were planted on 775,000 square meters across Bosnia and Herzegovina as part of this project.

2. Fruit Planting Project

As part of the autumn planting in 2016, the Waqf Directorate established long-term fruit plantations on *Waqf* land in Vlasenica and Bratunac. In Vlasenica, 10.000 sq. meters of land were cultivated with walnuts, apples, and plums, while another 10.000 m² in Bratunac were planted with grafted walnut trees. The Waqf Directorate also financed the planting of 180 walnut saplings in the Jablanica *Jamaat* within the Tešanj Islamic Community Municipality. (Report on Walnut Planting in Jablanica *Jamaat*, 2017)

3. Raspberry Planting

In 2016, the Waqf Directorate financed the planting of 4,000 raspberry saplings on more than 5,000 square meters in Čelić, with the necessary materials provided. (Agreement on the realization of the project of raising raspberry plantations on the waqf plot, 2016)

4. Financial Support for Individual *Majlis*' Projects

The Waqf Directorate continually provides financial support to *Majlis* municipalities for the implementation of fruit planting and agricultural land cultivation projects.

PROJECTS OF THE *MAJLIS* MUNICIPALITIES

The *Majlis* municipalities of the Islamic Community usually possess varying amounts of agricultural land within their territories. The level of utilization and success varies depending on the geographical location, financial capabilities to hire labor, and the number of employees within the *Majlis*. In this section, we will present several successful examples of revitalizing unused *Waqf* land.

MIC Čelić is located in the northern part of Bosnia and Herzegovina. The *Waqfs* in this *Majlis* are fragmented and small in size, mostly consisting of orchards and arable land. The total area of the land plots is 700,000 square meters, of which 40% is arable. According to 2024 data, 66% of the 102 agricultural plots are either rented or directly used by the local community, 31% remain unused and overgrown, and 3% have been illegally seized by neighbours. The *Majlis* has a registered agricultural estate within the municipality. (Enhancing the *Waqf* Property of the Islamic Community Čelić, 2022)

Graph 2*UTILIZATION OF WAQF PLOTS IN MIC ČELIĆ*

Presentation of the utilization of waqf plots based on the data of MIZ Čelić.

The usage in Graph 2 refers to the regular and occasional use directly by the Jamaat; usage without a contract mainly refers to the use of fruit orchard yields, while the usurped lands are smaller areas where unauthorized structures have been built. The reasons for not using the plots vary, such as distance from the inhabited area, poor soil quality, small area size, frequent flooding, etc.

A positive example from this Majlis is the "United Waqf," a collection of plots that are used, leased, and maintained according to an agreement between three Jamaats, with profits shared proportionally. (Enhancing the Waqf property of the Islamic Community Čelić, 2022)

Although it has relatively good results and a high level of land use, the Majlis aims to ensure further efficiency through planned investments. The investment plan aims to establish 20 dunams of greenhouses, dig 10 wells with water pumps, plant 50 dunams of orchards, build a cold storage facility, and improve access roads. According to analyses, the return on investment is high, with an expected payback period of 5 years. (Enhancing the Waqf property of the Islamic Community Čelić, 2022)

MIC Bijeljina is located in the northeast of Bosnia and Herzegovina, in the fertile plains where the Drina meets the Sava. Since 2014, the Majlis has been implementing a project to improve the use of waqf property. MIC Bijeljina owns 15 hectares of agricultural land, which it cultivates with its own machinery and labor, and additionally cultivates land owned by Jamaat members for a monetary fee. The area of additional land the Majlis cultivates has increased each year, reaching 25 hectares in 2018 and 70 hectares by 2021. The proceeds from agriculture have been used to purchase machinery, irrigation systems, etc., creating new jobs, and demonstrating that investing in agricultural land pays off.

MIC Bijeljina is an example of how well-planned investment in its own production and workforce can greatly increase revenue compared to renting property. The Majlis' spring and fall sowing projects are also financially supported by the Waqf Directorate. (Autumn wheat sowing on the waqf agricultural estate of MIC Bijeljina, 2023) MIC Bijeljina has also established its own agricultural estate "Waqf Agricultural Estate Bijeljina." (Agreement on the realization of the project of raising wheat and barley plantations on the waqf plot, 2019). When it comes to investment profitability, according to Majlis reports, total revenues from corn sowing alone amount to around 180% of invested funds, although in the reporting year 2021, revenues were reduced by about 50% due to drought. (Report on yields achieved as part of the agricultural planting project on the waqf agricultural estate of MIC Bijeljina, 2022).

Graph 3

CULTIVATED AREA OF MAJLIS FROM BIJELJINA IN 1000 m².

Presentation of the increase in arable land in Majlis IC Bijeljina according to Majlis' reports to the Waqf Directorate.

MIC Janja, located about 30 kilometers south of Bijeljina, owns 200.000 square meters of agricultural land and additionally cultivates agricultural land belonging to members of the Islamic community. The Majlis' projects include the sowing of wheat and corn, as well as the cultivation of potatoes, in cooperation with the Waqf Directorate and the agricultural cooperative from Janja. As part of the land cultivation project, they secured working machinery and employed several workers who performed tasks related to the improvement of waqf property. (Spring sowing and potato cultivation on the waqf of MIC Janja. Request for donation as part of the "Improvement of Waqf" project, 2018). In 2022 alone, seasonal agricultural income was used to invest in the purchase of two trailers and the acquisition of 11.000 m² of land, and 3 tons of potatoes and 1.5 tons of flour were donated. (Report on yields achieved as part of the agricultural planting project on waqf land, 2022).

Although Majlises that strategically develop waqf land, turning to their own production or renting, successfully operate with a surplus, investing tens of thousands of KM in machinery and the purchase of new land, their reliance on additional financial assistance for planting from the Waqf Directorate and public tenders from

various levels of government indicates that an adequate level of agricultural machinery scale and quality has not yet been achieved.

CHALLENGES IN WORK

Although the potential of agricultural waqfs in the modern era exists, their revitalization is not without challenges. In this section, we will present the main challenges of initiating and developing agricultural waqfs:

1. Fragmentation of plots suitable for agricultural development. Although there are relatively many waqfs in Bosnia and Herzegovina, they are not structurally suitable for larger plantations, and thus not for significant and purposeful use of agricultural machinery in production, except in northern B&H in the mentioned examples.
2. Low profitability results from insufficient possibilities for using agricultural machinery and increasing labor engagement, which leads to a withdrawal from agricultural production that exceeds personal needs and is oriented toward trade, export, etc.
3. Agricultural income is mostly seasonal for individuals and not regular monthly income, due to the absence of agricultural cooperatives. Majlises can establish cooperatives, which require dedication, significant land areas, a plan, and initial resources. An additional challenge is inflation and the rising cost of seeds, fertilizers, and labor.
4. Starting production, acquiring tools and machinery, and financing labor require initial investments until a satisfactory scale and quality are achieved, which can take years, assuming that investment can be realized from its own income after a certain period.
5. The possibility and strategy for product placement often lacking, leading to price fluctuations in direct sales, which further reduce the profitability of agricultural production.
6. Absence of development strategies at higher levels, which would partly satisfy the market with halal, healthy, and domestic products, but also maintain prices that would justify further investment and engagement in agriculture, thereby avoiding large price fluctuations, reducing profitability, and contributing to inflation.
7. **Engaging expert personnel for market analysis, local development strategies, and soil quality** requires additional investment in personnel, especially during the initial phase of production.
8. **The constant outflow of the population abroad and the competitiveness of the labor market** pose challenges for all Balkan countries, and according

to all competitiveness parameters with the EU market, B&H is generally at about 50%.

9. **Decentralization of waqf management in B&H** represents an obstacle to significantly investing waqf revenues back into the waqfs themselves, prioritizing development projects, and achieving independence from unstable external support.

FUTURE ROLE OF WAQF IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LOCAL COMMUNITIES

Modern trends of rising food prices, as well as a decline in food quality, are increasingly prompting the Majlises of the Islamic Community that have unused agricultural land to think more about ensuring those types of food can be produced in Bosnia and Herzegovina, as well as securing financial benefits and putting waqf assets to use.

The long-term strategy for the development of waqf in Bosnia and Herzegovina aims to address the challenges faced by waqf property. This includes activating unpromising waqf plots by planting perennial trees or afforestation, as well as applying adequate established methods for using waqf land. In the upcoming period, more and more Majlises have concrete plans for cultivation or wish to explore the possibilities, justification, and quality of utilizing agricultural waqf land. These include the following Majlises: Bihać, Donji Waqf, Jajce, Zenica, Bijeljina, Čelić, Puračić, Srebrenik, and Zvornik.

A positive aspect indicating the potential of agriculture, besides the current extent of waqf land, is the increasing number of properties being endowed year after year (see Graph 3). Due to the fact that a large portion of agricultural waqf land is fragmented and sometimes inaccessible, planning and implementing significant projects requires activities aimed at land consolidation to create larger areas, which is already being realized to a certain extent.

Graph 4

NUMBER OF ENDOWED PROPERTIES ANNUALLY IN B&H

Source: Strategy for development of Waqf and the Waqf Directorate of the IC in B&H 2025-2034 (2024).

According to official statistics from the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, the relative share of formally employed individuals in agriculture out of the total number of employees is quite low, approximately 2%, although this number is steadily increasing, while the total share in this sector is around 10%. According to the aforementioned statistics, 86% of farmers are over 40 years old (Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development FB&H 2021-2027, p. 7). In the same entity, 52.36% of the population lives in rural areas.

Based on the success rate of previously implemented projects by the Waqf Directorate and Majlis, their plans, and the existing challenges in their work, we can consider the future role through the following points:

1. Through better organization, cultivation, and infrastructure investments, waqf lands can become an important source of agricultural production. Seed sowing, fruit planting, and greenhouse production projects in these Majlises show a positive trend, which can serve as a model for others.
2. Without addressing the challenges of production, product placement, and the profitability of engaging in agriculture, it is not possible to create adequate long-term plans and solutions. Given that the Islamic Community has limited resources for economic development and that earning income is not its primary activity except to the extent that ensures its financial independence, it has not adequately addressed these challenges so far, which still represent important issues at the start of any agricultural startup. Although it is not an optimal solution, leasing waqf land is a profitable and currently the best possible option in most of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Monograph MIC Čelić, 2024). This method of use is sustainable and should be anticipated in the future.
3. The organization in the form of agricultural cooperatives operating at the Majlis level or in broader areas could help increase efficiency and reduce costs, enable mass production, and improve access to incentives, but it would also require more serious organization and strategic planning, which represents a significant step in the long-term development of waqf. Additionally, it is necessary to take advantage of the significant increase in agricultural investments at the cantonal and entity levels of government, where annual investments are measured in millions of KM, with further increases expected since agricultural competitiveness has not yet been achieved, nor has a satisfactory level of quality for machinery and grain drying and storage facilities (Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development FB&H 2021-2027, p. 9). Such incentives can be utilized through agricultural cooperatives.

4. Economically speaking, greenhouse production is more suitable and profitable for smaller agricultural areas in populated places, and it has a clearer profit projection, which is particularly significant considering the structure of waqfs in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Greenhouse production also represents an opportunity for Majlises with smaller areas of waqf land to generate income and utilize it.
5. Projects from the Waqf Directorate demonstrate varying degrees of success due to the fact that many Majlises participating in the projects did not have adequate market analysis, needs assessment, soil quality evaluation, or the necessary human factors to ensure the survival of the crops planted. Since the Waqf Directorate does not have complete insight into the readiness to manage waqf in the field, future projects of the Waqf Directorate will need to consider the previous results of the Majlises.
6. Regarding the social role of waqf, its perspective lies in the development of sustainable agriculture and food security, as well as humanitarian projects such as food donations.
7. With planned development and an increase in food production volume, it is realistic to expect a more significant role for waqf in reducing the depopulation of rural areas by retaining the population through employment opportunities, as well as improving the infrastructure of rural communities, which would generally enhance living conditions and create new opportunities for local economic development.

CONCLUSION

Waqfs, as one of the fundamental pillars of Islamic tradition, play a significant role in the socio-economic development of Bosnia and Herzegovina. This paper analyses the role of agricultural waqf in the context of modern challenges and the potential for the development of local communities. Agricultural waqf land, although underutilized, has the potential to become a significant factor in the economic revitalization of rural and suburban areas.

The experiences of the Waqf Directorate and Majlis demonstrate that, with adequate planning and expert support, waqf properties can contribute to increasing local food production, empowering local communities through employment, and creating self-sustainable projects. Examples of successfully implemented projects, such as grain sowing, fruit planting, and greenhouse production, show that waqf can achieve significant economic potential while also fulfilling religious and humanitarian obligations towards the community.

However, challenges such as land fragmentation, low profitability, lack of agricultural machinery, and weak institutional support still pose obstacles to fully developing the potential of waqf agriculture. Therefore, it is essential for the Islamic Community and relevant authorities to intensify efforts to address these issues, improve planning, and

increase investments in infrastructure and machinery. Projects aimed at revitalizing and strengthening waqfs certainly deserve the support of the Community.

In the future, agricultural waqfs have the potential not only to provide halal and healthy food for the domestic market but also to play an important role in reducing depopulation in rural areas, strengthening the local economy, and enhancing social cohesion. Utilizing waqf land through sustainable agricultural practices can significantly contribute to the development of the community and local areas, ensuring long-term benefits for society as a whole.

In this way, agricultural waqfs can become not only a means of preserving Islamic tradition but also a catalyst for sustainable development and social justice in a contemporary context.

REFERENCES

1. *Agreement on the realization of the project of raising wheat and barley plantations on the waqf plot*, Waqf Directorate and MIC Bijeljina, 13.11.2019.
2. *Agreement on the realization of the project of raising raspberry plantations on the waqf plot*, Waqf Directorate and MIC Čelić, 08.11.2016.
3. Avdibašić, E., Rahmanović, Dž. (2024), *Monograph MIC Čelić*, Waqf Directorate and Majlis IC Čelić.
4. *Enhancing the Waqf property of the Islamic Community Čelić* (2022), [Unpublished document], Majlis IC Čelić.
5. Kahf, M (2013), *The role of Waqf in improving the Ummah welfare*, International Seminar on Waqf as a Private Legal Body.
6. Majlis IC Bijeljina (2023), *Autumn wheat sowing on the waqf agricultural estate of MIC Bijeljina* [Unpublished document], Majlis IC Bijeljina.
7. Majlis IC Bijeljina (2022), *Report on yields achieved as part of the agricultural planting project on the waqf agricultural estate of MIC Bijeljina* [Unpublished document], Majlis IC Bijeljina
8. Majlis IC Janja (2022), *Report on yields achieved as part of the agricultural planting project on waqf land* [Unpublished document], Majlis IC Janja.
9. Majlis IC Janja (2019), *Spring sowing and potato cultivation on the waqf of MIC Janja. Request for donation as part of the "Improvement of Waqf" project* [Unpublished document], Majlis IC Janja.
10. Majlis IC Vlasenica (2017), *Report on Walnut Planting in Jablanica Jamaat* [Unpublished document], Majlis IC Vlasenica.
11. *Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development FB&H 2021-2027* (2021), Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Water Management and Forestry.
12. *Strategy for development of Waqf and the Waqf Directorate of the IC in B&H 2025-2034* (2024), Waqf Directorate.